

Non-indexed references in small open access journals: A hidden scientific discourse?

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Abstract

The scholarly publication system is dominated by large corporate publishers, who publish most of the scientific research. Estimates show that more than half of all publications in the Web of Science come from the five largest publishers, and in the social sciences this share rises considerably more. Yet, small academic publishers (commonly associated with universities, learned societies, or scientific groups with shared research agendas) also play an important role in scholarly communication beyond the indexing by well-known bibliometric databases. Thus, academic incentives may vary significantly between the two groups, particularly regarding the publishing patterns they follow. This poster shows specific bibliometric data highlighting differences and similarities between journals' references indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus and those that are not. Specifically, this contribution looks at small publishers and their respective journals along the open/closed access formats. The goal is to problematize and assess the visibility and meaning of literature being cited in indexed journals against the literature not listed in these databases. This can shed light into the scientific practices and narratives of different academic disciplines that are defined more nationally or internationally.

Introduction

Assuming a novel approach to examine the role of small academic publishers, this research focuses on the differences within open access (OA) journals. Small OA journals hence play an important intermediary role for specific scholarly communities, defined by regional, cultural, linguistic, or thematic foci (usually associated with universities, learned societies, or scientific groups). They are also a counterpart to the larger, corporate publishers that dominate the academic publishing landscape, as they represent more specific academic narratives (Kaier & Lackner, 2019).

By exploring two of the main bibliometric databases available (the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus), the goal is to highlight the visibility and relevance of publications that fall outside the scope of database indexation and assess, through an exploratory analysis, the role that these journals play in contributing to the creation and/or expansion of a particular scientific discourse. Scientific discourses will be understood here as shared epistemic backgrounds linked by citation practices based on background or proximity (see Hyland, 1999).

Data and Methods

Data comes from the Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie's (KB) in-house version of the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases. The analysis focuses on articles and reviews published in journals between 2010 and 2020, covering most citation count windows for a broad selection of articles and reviews (*document type*) published in journals (*source type*). The analysis is based on a subsample of OA journals, managed by small publishers (it

follows Stephen and Stahlschmidt's (2022) approach to defining and identifying small publishers). Table 1 shows the detailed breakdown of the data in each category and for each stage in the (pre-)processing workflow.

Individual items were grouped by journal and publisher, and a threshold of OA content was defined to classify the journals as such. Following, only highly cited (HC) items (belonging to the top 10% cited items in their field and publishing year) were selected (see Table 2). The analysis investigates the disciplinary differences and their dimensions regarding citing patterns in these HC items. Hence, grouped by journal, publisher and discipline, this approach sheds light into the different practices, and the particular scholarly narratives and epistemic backgrounds supporting top research output.

Findings

The analysis shows that only a fraction of items published in the 2010-2020 period come from OA journals (~13%). Further, a smaller proportion of these are published in *small* OA journals, that is, on journals not belonging to large corporate publishers and which publish less than 240 items per year (~4%). When looking only at those items considered HC in their respective fields, the proportion is reduced further (47k items with ~3mill references, mean = 64.4 references/item, see Table 2).

References are the key component we look at when analysing the scientific discourses in the background of these OA-HC items. We consider the way in which particular non-indexed materials make their way into HC literature to function as a bridging mechanism for these epistemic practices and narratives. For example, there is an important

proportion of references from this HC items that is not indexed in either database (27.6%). This proportion is, however, highly skewed towards the social sciences and humanities (SSH) fields (see Figure 1). In contrary, virtually all references from the medical and health sciences fields are listed. This marks and gives evidence of a distinct approach to epistemic practices relating to knowledge production and the visibility of said knowledge. The stark difference in absolute and relative values, as well as the specific journals' characteristics highlight this dynamic.

Table 1. Publication distribution in WoS and Scopus, by publisher size and OA (2010-2020).

All	WoS	Scopus	Total
P	4,190	10,234 ^a	14,424
J	15,972	32,854	48,826
I	17,045,823 (100)	21,938,502 (100)	38,984,325 (100)
OA			
P	1,691	4,565	6,256
J	4,236	10,393	14,629
I	4,199,413 (24.6)	5,314,253 (24.2)	9,513,666 (24.4)
SOA^b			
P	1,432	5,852	7,744
J	1,662	5,612	7,329
I	456,169 (3.0)	797,144 (4.0)	1,253,313 (3.5)

Note: P: Publishers, J: Journals, I: Items. OA: Open Access, SOA: Small Open Access. Percentages in parentheses. a/ At least 5mill items do not have complete publisher information. b/ Adding to Stephen and Stahlschmidt (2022), matching and exclusion was also done on the number of journals owned based on the list by Nishikawa-Pacher (2022).

Small OA journals, and the articles and reviews that achieve a HC count, offer independent channels of communication, especially for disciplines and scholars with specific research foci, and enrich academic discourse by enabling various actors to participate. Relevant scholarship published in these outlets also shows how dissimilar (and seemingly structural) epistemic practices can be regarding the scholarly background portrayed through them (27.6%). The scientific discourses found in non-indexed references are then mediated and reach the mainstream databases through scholarly links from this influential research. This bridging function makes thematic debates around key topics in various disciplines more visible. Further work needs to be undertaken to understand the specific role they play argumentatively.

Table 2. Reference Characteristics for Highly Cited (All Years) Items of Small OA Journals in Wos and Scopus (2010-2020).

	WoS	Scopus	Total
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HC Items*	52,797 (42.7)	70,926 (57.3)	123,723 (100)
Total References	3,146,201 (-)	4,238,421 (-)	7,384,622 (-)
Unique References	2,035,044 (100)	2,797,566 (100)	4,832,610 (100)
Indexed References	1,689,157 (83.0)	2,047,011 (73.1)	3,736,168 (77.3)
Non-Indexed References	345,887 (17.0)	750,555 (26.9)	1,096,442 (22.7)

Note: */ Total number of items included in the HC (top 10%) group counting all years after publication. Percentages in parentheses.

Figure 1. Proportion of indexed and non-indexed references in Scopus (2010-2020).

References

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